

Intrinsic Bayesian Errors-in-Variables Under Anisotropic Noise

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Abstract—We present an intrinsic Bayesian formulation of the linear errors-in-variables problem under anisotropic Gaussian noise using a homogeneous representation. By analytically marginalizing latent noise-free data, a closed-form marginal likelihood is obtained in arbitrary dimension. Under an ellipsoidal normalization, the resulting maximum likelihood estimator coincides with generalized total least squares. Bayesian inference is developed on an affine chart via homogenization, yielding an explicit posterior decomposition into a heavy-tailed radial component and an affine Gaussian term with a chart-dependent correction factor, and ensuring posterior properness under a Gaussian prior. A conditionally conjugate variational approximation enables efficient inference and admits a recursive implementation with exponential forgetting, resulting in a practical online variational EIV algorithm with closed-form updates. The method is illustrated on an application-motivated melt-flow-rate identification problem from plastic recycling, with anisotropic measurement noise and direct comparison to a numerically computed reference posterior. The example is used to assess recursive tracking and posterior-approximation quality under slight model misspecification.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the anisotropic linear errors-in-variables (EIV) model, latent variables $\bar{a} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\bar{b} \in \mathbb{R}$ satisfy the linear relation

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{b} &= \theta^T \bar{a}, \\ \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{a} \\ \bar{b} \end{bmatrix} + \varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where only the noisy observations (a, b) are available, with the noise being represented by $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$. Throughout, we assume that the measurement noise ε is zero-mean Gaussian with known, generally anisotropic covariance matrix. The goal of this paper is to establish a fully specified Bayesian formulation of linear errors-in-variables model, rigorously characterize posterior and its properness conditions, and yield a principled recursive inference algorithm with uncertainty quantification.

Historically, Bayesian treatments of errors-in-variables models have predominantly relied on latent noise-free covariates, yielding high dimensional hierarchical models whose inference typically requires Markov chain Monte Carlo methods even in linear-Gaussian settings [1], [2], [3]. Such formulations are flexible, but they do not yield a closed-form likelihood in the parameter of interest and therefore do not make explicit the

connection to classical total least-squares (TLS) and generalized total least-squares (GTLS) estimators, here collectively denoted by (G)TLS [4], [5]. In parallel, classical (G)TLS methods have primarily focused on point estimation, with uncertainty characterization treated mainly through asymptotic covariance analysis [6], [7], [8].

An alternative perspective emerged in the computer vision literature, where likelihood functions for TLS-type problems were derived by marginalizing latent, noise-free measurements [9]. These formulations established that TLS arises as a maximum likelihood estimator under Gaussian measurement noise. However, the analysis in this line of work remained largely confined to point estimation and Cramér–Rao-type uncertainty bounds, without constructing or studying the full posterior distribution.

More recently, variational Bayesian formulations have been proposed for recursive total least squares estimation with uncertainty quantification and forgetting [10]. These methods yield computationally tractable recursive TLS-type estimators via a fixed-form variational approximation with structural constraints, but rely on a restricted posterior family rather than an exact Bayesian treatment. Bayesian extensions to the anisotropic case, including our earlier work on Bayesian GTLS [11], likewise employ approximations during model derivation in order to retain algebraic equivalence with classical (G)TLS estimators. While these approaches successfully recover (G)TLS solutions and yield practical recursive algorithms, the use of approximations obscures the intrinsic structure of the exact EIV likelihood. As a result, questions of analytic posterior form, posterior properness conditions, and a fully exact n -dimensional Bayesian treatment under general anisotropic noise remain open.

In this paper, we adopt a homogeneous reformulation of the EIV model (1), originally introduced for isotropic EIV in our earlier work [12]. This geometric perspective enables the derivation of closed-form dataset likelihoods by analytically marginalizing the latent noise-free variables, yielding an intrinsic likelihood expressed directly in the projective parameter. The maximum likelihood of resulting formulation, under an appropriate projective gauge, yields a generalized eigenvalue problem whose solution is equivalent to GTLS. By composing this intrinsic likelihood with homogenization, we obtain a structured posterior on the affine chart whose decomposition cleanly separates projectively invariant components from chart-dependent terms and leads to an explicit condition for posterior properness. Leveraging the resulting posterior structure, we derive a conditionally conjugate variational approximation and a recursive variational inference algorithm with closed-form updates and exponential forgetting following the discounted Bayesian recursion of Peterka [13].

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The framework is illustrated on an application-motivated sequential identification example from plastic recycling, chosen to compare the recursive approximation against both GTLS and a numerically evaluated reference posterior.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II derives the marginal likelihoods and establishes their connection to GTLS. Section III formulates the Bayesian posterior and analyzes its structure on the affine chart. Section IV develops a conjugate variational approximation, and Section V derives a recursive inference algorithm. Section VI provides an experimental validation in an online identification setting.

Throughout the paper, $\mathcal{N}(\cdot | \mu, \Sigma)$ and $t_\nu(\cdot | m, S)$ denote the multivariate normal and Student- t distributions with location and scale parameters (μ, Σ) and (m, S) , respectively. The inverse-gamma $\text{IG}(\cdot | \alpha, \beta)$ distribution is parametrized in the shape–scale form, whereas the gamma $\text{Ga}(\cdot | \alpha, \beta)$ distribution is parametrized in the shape–rate form. Whenever a distributional factor is used only up to proportionality, we append the subscript ker .

II. BAYESIAN LIKELIHOOD AND STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF EIV

Defining the latent vector $\bar{d} := [\bar{a}^T, \bar{b}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$, the explicit regression model (1) admits the equivalent homogeneous form

$$0 = \vartheta^T \bar{d}, \quad \vartheta \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} \setminus \{0\}, \quad (2)$$

where $\vartheta \propto [\theta^T, -1]^T$; we write $\vartheta = [\vartheta_{1:n}^T, \vartheta_{n+1}]^T$. Since (2) is invariant under nonzero scaling of ϑ , the parameter is naturally defined on the real projective space $\mathbb{RP}^n := (\mathbb{R}^{n+1} \setminus \{0\}) / \sim$, where \sim identifies nonzero vectors up to scaling; $[\vartheta]$ denotes the class of ϑ . We use two representations of $[\vartheta]$:

I. Spherical representation: $\vartheta \in \mathbb{S}^n := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} : \|x\|_2 = 1\}$, $\vartheta \sim -\vartheta$, which induces the canonical a double cover of \mathbb{RP}^n and fixes the scale up to sign;

II. Affine representation: on the chart $\vartheta_{n+1} \neq 0$, each $[\vartheta]$ admits a unique representative satisfying $\vartheta_{n+1} = -1$, yielding the parameterization $\vartheta = [\theta^T, -1]^T$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

The mappings between representations are defined by the continuous, and hence Borel measurable, homogenization and dehomogenization maps

$$\Psi : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \{\vartheta \in \mathbb{S}^n : \vartheta_{n+1} < 0\}, \quad \Psi(\theta) = \frac{[\theta^T, -1]^T}{\sqrt{\|\theta\|_2^2 + 1}}, \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi : \{\vartheta \in \mathbb{S}^n : \vartheta_{n+1} \neq 0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n, \quad \Phi(\vartheta) = -\vartheta_{1:n} / \vartheta_{n+1}, \quad (4)$$

with $\Phi \circ \Psi = \text{id}$. All representations correspond to the same projective parameter $[\vartheta]$; the choice of representation affects only the parameterization, not the underlying model.

The observed dataset $D = \{d_i\}_{i=1}^N$ satisfies $d_i = \bar{d}_i + \varepsilon_i$, with independent and identically distributed noise $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_d)$ with known positive definite covariance $\Sigma_d \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}$. The latent variables $\bar{d}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$ satisfy the exact linear constraint $\vartheta^T \bar{d}_i = 0, \forall i$. In a Bayesian formulation, this constraint is encoded via the Dirac generalized distribution $\delta(\cdot)$, defined by $\int f(x) \delta(x-a) dx = f(a)$. With a slight abuse of notation, $p(\bar{d}_i | \vartheta) \propto \delta(\vartheta^T \bar{d}_i)$, meaning that the conditional distribution is supported on $\{\bar{d} : \vartheta^T \bar{d} = 0\}$. This yields the marginal datum

likelihood

$$p(d_i | \vartheta, \Sigma_d) \propto \int_{\mathbb{R}^{n+1}} \mathcal{N}(d_i | \bar{d}_i, \Sigma_d) \delta(\vartheta^T \bar{d}_i) d\bar{d}_i. \quad (5)$$

Lemma 1 (marginal datum likelihood): For any $\Sigma_d \succ 0$, any $\vartheta \in \mathbb{S}^n$, and any $d_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$,

$$p(d_i | \vartheta, \Sigma_d) \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\vartheta^T d_i)^2}{2\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta}\right). \quad (6)$$

Proof: Using symmetry, $\mathcal{N}(d_i | \bar{d}_i, \Sigma_d) = \mathcal{N}(\bar{d}_i | d_i, \Sigma_d)$, the integral in (5) equals $\mathbb{E}_{\bar{d}_i \sim \mathcal{N}(d_i, \Sigma_d)} [\delta(\vartheta^T \bar{d}_i)]$. Let $Z = \vartheta^T \bar{d}_i$. Then Z is Gaussian with mean $\vartheta^T d_i$ and variance $\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta$. Hence

$$\mathbb{E}[\delta(Z)] = p_Z(0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi, \vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\vartheta^T d_i)^2}{2\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta}\right), \quad (7)$$

which proves the claim. \blacksquare

Aggregating the dataset into the scatter matrix yields a quadratic form in ϑ , and hence a closed-form likelihood.

Lemma 2 (dataset likelihood): Let $D = \{d_i\}_{i=1}^N$, $\Sigma_d \succ 0$, and $\vartheta \in \mathbb{S}^n$. Define the scatter matrix

$$\Omega_d := \sum_{i=1}^N d_i d_i^T \in \mathbb{R}^{(n+1) \times (n+1)}, \quad \Omega_d \succeq 0. \quad (8)$$

Under conditional independence,

$$p(D | \vartheta, \Sigma_d) \propto (\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta)^{-N/2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\vartheta^T \Omega_d \vartheta}{\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta}\right). \quad (9)$$

Proof: From Lemma 1 and conditional independence,

$$\begin{aligned} p(D | \vartheta, \Sigma_d) &\propto \prod_{i=1}^N (\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta)^{-1/2} \exp\left(-\frac{(\vartheta^T d_i)^2}{2\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta}\right) \\ &\propto (\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta)^{-N/2} \exp\left(-\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (\vartheta^T d_i)^2}{2\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Using $\sum_{i=1}^N (\vartheta^T d_i)^2 = \vartheta^T (\sum_{i=1}^N d_i d_i^T) \vartheta$ and (8), the numerator sum becomes $\vartheta^T \Omega_d \vartheta$, yielding (9). \blacksquare

All mappings and densities considered are Borel measurable, the prior is absolutely continuous with respect to the relevant base measure, and the Dirac distribution is interpreted in the standard distributional sense.

Since $\Sigma_d \succ 0$, the likelihood (9) is continuous on the compact sphere \mathbb{S}^n , and therefore bounded. Hence, any finite prior measure on \mathbb{S}^n yields a proper posterior on \mathbb{S}^n . This property is preserved under measurable reparameterization at the level of the induced measure, although the corresponding density expression depends on the chosen representation.

The following corollary establishes the connection to (G)TLS by introducing an ellipsoidal representation that complements the spherical and affine parameterizations.

Corollary 1 (Reduction to (G)TLS with ellipsoidal gauge): In the ellipsoidal representation (gauge) defined by $\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta = 1$, the likelihood (9) reduces to

$$p(D | \vartheta, \Sigma_d) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \vartheta^T \Omega_d \vartheta\right). \quad (11)$$

Under this normalization, the likelihood is equivalent in functional form to the Bayesian GTLS likelihood in [11, Eq. 4.17]. In the isotropic case $\Sigma_d = \sigma^2 I$, it further reduces, up to an equivalent projective rescaling, to the Bayesian TLS likelihood

in [14, Eq. 4]. Consequently, the maximum-likelihood estimate is obtained as

$$\hat{\vartheta} = \arg \min_{\vartheta \neq 0} \frac{\vartheta^T \Omega_d \vartheta}{\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta} = \arg \min_{\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta = 1} \vartheta^T \Omega_d \vartheta, \quad (12)$$

which yields the classical GTLS solution direction, and in the isotropic case the classical TLS solution direction.

Proof: Substituting $\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta = 1$ into (9) removes the prefactor and yields the stated quadratic form. Thus, maximizing the likelihood is equivalent to minimizing $\vartheta^T \Omega_d \vartheta$ subject to $\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta = 1$. The stationarity condition for the Lagrangian $\mathcal{J}(\vartheta, \lambda) = \vartheta^T \Omega_d \vartheta + \lambda(\vartheta^T \Sigma_d \vartheta - 1)$ gives

$$\Omega_d \vartheta = \mu \Sigma_d \vartheta \quad (13)$$

for some scalar μ . This is the GTLS generalized eigenproblem. For $\Sigma_d = \sigma^2 I$, it reduces to the TLS eigenproblem. ■

III. BAYESIAN POSTERIOR

Although inference is performed in the affine coordinates $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the likelihood is developed in homogeneous coordinates, which provide the geometric framework underlying the proposed model. The posterior on θ is then obtained by composing this likelihood with the homogenization map and combining it with a prior on θ .

Theorem 1 (Affine posterior via homogenization): Let $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^n$ have proper prior density $p(\theta)$ with respect to Lebesgue measure, and let $\vartheta = \Psi(\theta) \in \{\vartheta \in \mathbb{S}^n : \vartheta_{n+1} < 0\}$ denote the corresponding normalized homogeneous representation. Then the posterior density on the affine chart satisfies

$$p(\theta | D) \propto p(D | \Psi(\theta), \Sigma_d) p(\theta). \quad (14)$$

Proof: Let Π_θ denote the prior measure on \mathbb{R}^n with density $p(\theta)$. Define the induced prior on \mathbb{S}^n as the pushforward of Π_θ under Ψ , i.e., $\Pi_{\mathbb{S}}(A) = \Pi_\theta(\Psi^{-1}(A))$ for measurable $A \subset \mathbb{S}^n$.

The (unnormalized) posterior measure on \mathbb{S}^n is obtained by likelihood reweighting,

$$\Pi_{\mathbb{S}}^D(d\vartheta) \propto p(D | \vartheta, \Sigma_d) \Pi_{\mathbb{S}}(d\vartheta). \quad (15)$$

Pushing this measure forward to the affine chart via Φ yields, for $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$,

$$\Pi_\theta^D(B) = \Pi_{\mathbb{S}}^D(\Phi^{-1}(B)). \quad (16)$$

Since $\Phi \circ \Psi = \text{id}$ on the affine chart, it follows that

$$\Pi_\theta^D(d\theta) \propto p(D | \Psi(\theta), \Sigma_d) \Pi_\theta(d\theta). \quad (17)$$

As Π_θ admits density $p(\theta)$ with respect to $d\theta$, the posterior density yields (14), which completes the proof. ■

Theorem 1 characterizes the posterior via the homogeneous likelihood. The following theorem provides an explicit decomposition that enables analysis and variational approximation.

Theorem 2 (Affine posterior kernel decomposition):

Partition the scatter and noise covariance matrices as

$$\Omega_d = \begin{bmatrix} U & v \\ v^T & w \end{bmatrix}, \quad \Sigma_d = \begin{bmatrix} A & h \\ h^T & c \end{bmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

where $U, A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $v, h \in \mathbb{R}^n$, and $w, c \in \mathbb{R}$. Assume $\Sigma_d \succ 0$ and $\Omega_d \succ 0$. Then $U \succ 0$, $A \succ 0$, and $r = c - h^T A^{-1} h > 0$. Define

$\mu = U^{-1}v$, $m = A^{-1}h$, and $S = \frac{r}{v}A^{-1}$ for any $v > 0$, and let $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}(N - v - 2n) - 1$ and $\beta = \frac{1}{2}(w - v^T U^{-1}v)$. Then, on the affine chart, the posterior in (14) admits the decomposition

$$p(\theta | D) \propto t_{v, \ker}(\theta | m, S) \text{IG}_{\ker}(\lambda(\theta) | \alpha, \beta) \times \mathcal{N}(\theta | \mu, \lambda(\theta)U^{-1}) C(\theta) p(\theta), \quad (19)$$

where $C(\theta) = (\|\theta\|^2 + 1)^{N/2}$ and $\lambda(\theta) = \theta^T A \theta - 2h^T \theta + c$. The identity holds in the kernel sense, up to multiplicative constants independent of θ , and does not require the displayed factors to be normalizable.

Proof: Applying the block partitions (18) into the affine posterior kernel (14) gives, up to θ -independent constants,

$$p(\theta | D) \propto \lambda(\theta)^{-N/2} \exp\left(-\frac{\theta^T U \theta - 2v^T \theta + w}{2\lambda(\theta)}\right) C(\theta) p(\theta). \quad (20)$$

We verify that this kernel matches the product form in (19). Up to θ -independent constants, the three factors have kernels

$$t_{v, \ker}(\theta | m, S) \propto \left(1 + \frac{1}{v}(\theta - m)^T S^{-1}(\theta - m)\right)^{-(v+n)/2}, \quad (21)$$

$$\text{IG}_{\ker}(\lambda(\theta) | \alpha, \beta) \propto \lambda(\theta)^{-\alpha-1} \exp\left(-\frac{\beta}{\lambda(\theta)}\right), \quad (22)$$

$$\mathcal{N}(\theta | \mu, \lambda(\theta)U^{-1}) \propto \lambda(\theta)^{-n/2} \exp\left(-\frac{(\theta - \mu)^T U (\theta - \mu)}{2\lambda(\theta)}\right). \quad (23)$$

Using $S = \frac{r}{v}A^{-1}$ and $\lambda(\theta) = (\theta - m)^T A (\theta - m) + r$, we have

$$1 + \frac{1}{v}(\theta - m)^T S^{-1}(\theta - m) = \frac{\lambda(\theta)}{r}, \quad (24)$$

hence $t_{v, \ker}(\theta | m, S) \propto \lambda(\theta)^{-(v+n)/2}$. Multiplying powers of $\lambda(\theta)$ gives $\lambda(\theta)^{-N/2}$ since $\alpha = \frac{N-v-2n}{2} - 1$. Combining exponentials yields

$$\exp\left(-\frac{(\theta - \mu)^T U (\theta - \mu) + 2\beta}{2\lambda(\theta)}\right) = \exp\left(-\frac{\theta^T U \theta - 2v^T \theta + w}{2\lambda(\theta)}\right) \quad (25)$$

by $\mu = U^{-1}v$ and $\beta = \frac{1}{2}(w - v^T U^{-1}v)$. Thus, together with $C(\theta)p(\theta)$, the three displayed factors yield (19). ■

The restriction $\Omega_d \succ 0$ entails only a slight loss of generality, as it excludes only degenerate cases. Properness on \mathbb{S}^n carries over under measurable reparameterizations, including dehomogenization, but for the affine density this can be verified directly. Since $\Sigma_d \succ 0$, one has $\lambda(\theta) > 0$, and $\lambda(\theta)$ grows quadratically in $|\theta|$ as $|\theta| \rightarrow \infty$. Hence, the growth of $C(\theta)$ is canceled by $\lambda(\theta)^{-N/2}$, and their product remains bounded. Because the exponential term is bounded by 1, the likelihood is bounded. Thus, for the Gaussian prior $p(\theta) = \mathcal{N}(\mu_p, \Sigma_p)$ with $\Sigma_p \succ 0$ used below, the resulting posterior is integrable over \mathbb{R}^n and hence proper.

IV. CONJUGATE POSTERIOR APPROXIMATION

The decomposition in (19) suggests introducing auxiliary scale variables $\sigma > 0$ and $\omega > 0$, which yields the augmented mean-field family

$$q(\theta, \sigma, \omega) = q(\theta) q(\sigma) q(\omega). \quad (26)$$

Accordingly, we consider the augmented surrogate kernel

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{p}(\theta, \sigma, \omega) &\propto \tilde{C}(\theta) \mathcal{N}(\theta | \mu_p, \Sigma_p) \\ &\times \mathcal{N}(\theta | \mu, \sigma^{-1}U^{-1}) \text{Ga}_{\ker}(\sigma | \alpha, \beta) \\ &\times \exp\left(-\frac{\omega}{2}(\theta - m)^T S^{-1}(\theta - m)\right) \text{Ga}\left(\omega \mid \frac{v+n}{2}, \frac{v}{2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

We approximate (27) within the factorized family (26). The auxiliary variables σ and ω separate the scale-dependent terms and lead to closed-form updates of the variational factors. The remaining nonlinearity is contained in $\tilde{C}(\theta)$ and is handled by the quadratic surrogate introduced below.

Specifically, we use

$$\log \tilde{C}(\theta) = \log C(\theta_0) + g^T(\theta - \theta_0) + \frac{1}{2}(\theta - \theta_0)^T K(\theta - \theta_0), \quad (28)$$

where

$$g = N\theta_0(1 + \|\theta_0\|^2)^{-1},$$

$$K = \begin{cases} 0, & \|\theta_0\| < 1, \\ \frac{N(1 - \|\theta_0\|^2)}{(1 + \|\theta_0\|^2)^2} \frac{\theta_0\theta_0^T}{\|\theta_0\|^2}, & \|\theta_0\| \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

Here, K is rank-one negative semidefinite. This follows from the radial symmetry of $\log C(\theta)$: only the radial direction can contribute nonpositive curvature, whereas the tangential curvature is nonnegative. The surrogate therefore retains the radial curvature component and discards the tangential one.

Dropping constants independent of θ yields

$$\tilde{C}(\theta) \propto \exp(g^T(\theta - \theta_0) + \frac{1}{2}(\theta - \theta_0)^T K(\theta - \theta_0)). \quad (30)$$

Taking expectations with respect to $q(\sigma)$ and $q(\omega)$ yields a quadratic form in θ , and hence the optimal factor $q(\theta)$ is Gaussian.

$$q(\theta) = \mathcal{N}(\theta \mid \mu_q, \Sigma_q), \quad (31)$$

with precision

$$\Sigma_q^{-1} = \Sigma_p^{-1} + \mathbb{E}_{q(\sigma)}[\sigma]U + \mathbb{E}_{q(\omega)}[\omega]S^{-1} - K, \quad (32)$$

and mean

$$\mu_q = \Sigma_q(\Sigma_p^{-1}\mu_p + \mathbb{E}_{q(\sigma)}[\sigma]U\mu + \mathbb{E}_{q(\omega)}[\omega]S^{-1}m + g - K\theta_0); \quad (33)$$

since $K \preceq 0$, it follows that $\Sigma_q^{-1} \succ 0$.

The auxiliary factors follow from standard mean-field variational Bayes updates for Gaussian–Gamma conjugate structures [15, Ch. 10]. In particular, taking the expectation of the joint log-surrogate with respect to the remaining factors yields Gamma forms in σ and ω , with parameters determined by the corresponding expected quadratic forms under $q(\theta)$. The resulting updates are

$$q(\sigma) = \text{Ga}(\sigma \mid a_q, b_q), \quad a_q = \alpha + \frac{n}{2}, \quad (34)$$

$$b_q = \beta + \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[(\theta - \mu)^T U(\theta - \mu)],$$

$$q(\omega) = \text{Ga}(\omega \mid c_q, d_q), \quad c_q = \frac{\nu + n}{2}, \quad (35)$$

$$d_q = \frac{\nu}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[(\theta - m)^T S^{-1}(\theta - m)].$$

All expectations are available in closed form under $q(\theta)$. The surrogate center is updated iteratively with $\theta_0 \leftarrow \mu_q$, initialized at $\theta_0 = \mu_p$.

Because the mean-field factorization breaks the deterministic coupling between the auxiliary inverse scale σ and the intrinsic scale $\lambda(\theta)$, the conjugate VB updates may converge

to a fixed point whose implied scale is inconsistent with $\lambda(\theta)$. To partially restore this lost consistency, we impose the relaxed moment-matching consistency condition

$$\mathbb{E}_{q(\sigma)}[\sigma^{-1}] \approx \mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[\lambda(\theta)], \quad (36)$$

where

$$\mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[\lambda(\theta)] = \mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[\theta^T A \theta - 2h^T \theta + c]. \quad (37)$$

Rather than an exact coordinate-ascent update, this stabilization can be interpreted as an approximate variational projection that relaxes the conjugate update toward the consistency condition (36). Using $\mathbb{E}_{q(\sigma)}[\sigma^{-1}] = b_q/(a_q - 1)$, this yields the blended update

$$b_{q,\text{stab}} = (1 - \eta)b_q + \eta(a_q - 1)\mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[\lambda(\theta)], \quad (38)$$

where $\eta \in [0, 1)$ controls the convex interpolation. Larger values enforce stronger agreement with the nonlinear intrinsic scale induced by $\lambda(\theta)$, while moving the update further from the nominal VB step. The endpoints $\eta = 0$ and $\eta \rightarrow 1$ recover the nominal VB update and near-complete enforcement of the consistency correction, respectively. In the absence of a closed-form optimal selection rule, we set $\eta = 0.5$, which assigns equal weight to the two terms.

The variational Gamma factors are well defined provided $a_q > 0$, $b_q > 0$, $c_q > 0$, and $d_q > 0$. Here $c_q > 0$ and $d_q > 0$ for any $\nu > 0$. Moreover, under $\Omega_d \succ 0$, one has $U \succ 0$ and $\beta > 0$, which implies $b_q > 0$. Thus, the only remaining condition for the variational factor $q(\sigma)$ is $a_q > 0$. The auxiliary term $\text{Gaker}(\sigma \mid \alpha, \beta)$ in (27) is used only in kernel form, so $\alpha > 0$ is not required. The stabilized update (38) further requires $a_q > 1$, ensuring that $\mathbb{E}q(\sigma)[\sigma^{-1}]$ is finite. Since ν is auxiliary and larger values make these conditions more restrictive, we set $\nu = 1$.

V. RECURSIVE ALGORITHM DESIGN

In Algorithm 1, we implement the variational surrogate from the previous section in an online setting, processing one observation $d_i = [a_i^T, b_i]^T$ per iteration. Since both the surrogate and the discounted recursive approximation depend on the data only through the sufficient statistics (N_i, U_i, ν_i, w_i) , the algorithm propagates only these quantities. To maintain numerical conditioning over long data records and to track slowly varying parameters, the statistics are updated with exponential forgetting factor $\rho \in (0, 1]$, as in standard recursive identification [13]:

$$N_i = \rho N_{i-1} + 1, \quad U_i = \rho U_{i-1} + a_i a_i^T, \quad (39)$$

$$\nu_i = \rho \nu_{i-1} + a_i b_i, \quad w_i = \rho w_{i-1} + b_i^2.$$

This corresponds to the discounted posterior

$$p_\rho(\theta \mid D_i) \propto p(d_i \mid \theta) p_\rho(\theta \mid D_{i-1})^\rho p(\theta)^{1-\rho}, \quad (40)$$

so that older observations are exponentially downweighted and N_i acts as an effective sample size in all likelihood-dependent terms. Choosing $\rho \approx 1$ recovers near-batch behavior, whereas $\rho < 1$ enables adaptation.

Under exponential forgetting with $\rho < 1$, the Schur complement quantity β is not guaranteed to remain strictly positive.

This induces loss of curvature in the scale variable and may render the Gamma factor $q(\sigma)$ ill-defined. To ensure well-posed updates, the auxiliary Gamma parameters (a_q, b_q) are constrained to remain positive. In practice, nonpositive or near-degenerate values are replaced by a small constant $\varepsilon > 0$, acting as a numerical safeguard. The stabilized update (38) further requires $a_q > 1$.

At each time step, m_{vb} inner mean-field iterations update the auxiliary scale variables and the Gaussian posterior over θ , incorporating a rank-one correction induced by the chart factor. All updates are closed-form.

Algorithm 1 Online variational inference for anisotropic EIV

Require: Data $(a_i, b_i)_{i=1}^N$,
prior (μ_p, Σ_p) , noise covariance Σ_d ,
hyperparameters ν, ρ, η, m_{vb} .

Ensure: Variational posterior parameters (μ_q, Σ_q) .

- 1: Initialize sufficient statistics (N_0, U_0, v_0, w_0) and variational state $(\mu_q, \Sigma_q) \leftarrow (\mu_p, \Sigma_p)$.
- 2: **for** $i = 1, \dots, N$ **do**
- 3: Update (N_i, U_i, v_i, w_i) according to (39).
- 4: Form the likelihood-induced quantities μ, β, α, m, S .
- 5: **for** $t = 1, \dots, m_{vb}$ **do**
- 6: Update $\tilde{C}(\theta)$ at $\theta_0 = \mu_q$ according to (29).
- 7: Compute (a_q, b_q) according to (34).
- 8: **if** $a_q > 1$ **then**
- 9: Stabilize b_q according to (38).
- 10: **end if**
- 11: Enforce $a_q, b_q \geq \varepsilon$.
- 12: Set $q(\sigma) = \text{Ga}(\sigma | a_q, b_q)$.
- 13: Update $q(\omega)$ according to (35).
- 14: Update $q(\theta)$ according to (33) and (32).
- 15: **end for**
- 16: **end for**

The number of inner variational iterations is kept small, $m_{vb} \in [1, 5]$. As consecutive posteriors differ only incrementally, the variational fixed-point updates are initialized close to their solution, and only a few iterations per datum are sufficient for refinement.

VI. EXAMPLE: MFR TRACKING IN PLASTIC RECYCLING

To illustrate the proposed method in a practically relevant online-identification setting, we consider a simulation study motivated by polypropylene recycling, where the melt flow rate (MFR) of post-consumer material varies substantially within and across batches [16]. In the underlying process, MFR is estimated online and material with known MFR is added to reduce output variability [17], [18], [19], [20]. This motivates online identification of transient dynamics together with associated uncertainty. The example is chosen as a compact benchmark combining anisotropic-noise handling, recursive updating, comparison with GTLS, and comparison with a numerically evaluated reference posterior.

The transient dynamics are modeled as a first-order discrete-time system with unit static gain,

$$\bar{y}_i = \theta_i \bar{y}_{i-1} + (1 - \theta_i) \bar{u}_{i-1}, \quad (41)$$

Fig. 1. Recursive estimation of a piecewise constant parameter θ with a value change at $k = 90$. The figure shows the exponentially weighted GTLS estimate $\hat{\theta}_{\text{GTLS}}$, the mean of the reference posterior $p_p(\theta | D_i)$, and the mean of the Gaussian variational approximation $q(\theta)$, together with the true parameter θ_{true} . The shaded regions indicate the corresponding 95% HPD intervals for the reference posterior and the variational approximation.

where \bar{u}_i and \bar{y}_i denote the true input and output MFR signals, respectively. The parameter $\theta_i \in (0, 1)$ characterizes the first-order mixing dynamics of the process. In the simulation, θ_i is piecewise constant and undergoes an abrupt change at $i = 90$, corresponding to a material batch transition.

The measurements are corrupted by additive noise,

$$u_i = \bar{u}_i + \varepsilon_{u,i}, \quad y_i = \bar{y}_i + \varepsilon_{y,i}, \quad (42)$$

where $\varepsilon_{u,i} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_u^2)$ and $\varepsilon_{y,i} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_y^2)$.

Rearranging the model yields the implicit linear constraint (2). The corresponding data vectors are constructed from measured quantities as

$$d_i := \begin{bmatrix} y_{i-1} - u_{i-1} \\ y_i - u_{i-1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{y}_{i-1} - \bar{u}_{i-1} \\ \bar{y}_i - \bar{u}_{i-1} \end{bmatrix} + \varepsilon_i, \quad \Sigma_d = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 \\ \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_y^2 + \sigma_u^2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (43)$$

for $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \Sigma_d)$. This construction follows standard recursive (G)TLS practice with overlapping measurements. Consecutive vectors d_i and d_{i+1} share $y(i)$, which induces cross-sample dependence and formally violates conditional independence. The example is therefore interpreted as a practical benchmark under mild model misspecification.

Prior with $\mu_p = 0.65$ and $\Sigma_p = 0.2^2$ is adopted, reflecting prior knowledge that θ lies predominantly in $(0, 1)$. The algorithm is applied with $m_{vb} = 1$, which is sufficient due to the incremental nature of the updates. An exponential forgetting factor $\rho = 0.95$ is used, corresponding to an effective memory of $1/(1 - \rho) \approx 20$ samples, consistent with the expected timescale of parameter variation in the experiment. For reference, an exponentially weighted GTLS estimator with the same forgetting factor is included. The remaining hyperparameters are set to $\eta = 0.5$ and $\nu = 1$ as described in Section V; the results were observed to be insensitive to moderate variations of these values.

The simulation consists of 180 samples with measurement noise levels $\sigma_u = 0.08$ and $\sigma_y = 0.09$, and a parameter change from $\theta = 0.93$ to $\theta = 0.83$ at $i = 90$. The input signal exhibits slow stochastic variation with an offset change at the same time instant, providing excitation under nonstationary conditions. As shown in Figure 1, both GTLS and the proposed Gaussian variational approximation $q(\theta)$ track the parameter before and after the change. The simulation also permits

numerical evaluation of the mean and 95% HPD interval of the reference posterior $p_\rho(\theta | D_i)$ from (19), allowing direct comparison with $q(\theta)$. After the initial convergence phase, $q(\theta)$ closely matches $p_\rho(\theta | D_i)$ in both mean and HPD interval, indicating that the variational approximation accurately captures posterior location and uncertainty under exponential forgetting. The behavior of the method is robust with respect to the main tuning parameters: increasing η accelerates initial convergence, varying m_{vb} affects only the early transient phase, and the forgetting factor ρ governs the expected trade-off between adaptation speed and estimate smoothness.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced an intrinsic Bayesian formulation of the linear EIV problem under anisotropic Gaussian noise by representing the model on projective space. By analytically marginalizing the latent noise-free measurements, the formulation yields an exact closed-form marginal likelihood for both individual observations and full datasets. This intrinsic likelihood exposes the geometric structure of the problem, provides a probabilistic interpretation of GTLS, and recovers classical TLS under isotropic noise. Moreover, because posterior properness is established at the level of the projective posterior measure, it carries over under measurable reparameterizations, including the affine chart used for computation, even though the corresponding density expression is representation dependent. The resulting framework unifies geometric estimation and Bayesian inference in a finite-dimensional setting that supports both uncertainty quantification and online computation.

Building on the intrinsic formulation, the affine-chart posterior was derived explicitly and decomposed into interpretable geometric and probabilistic components, which underpin both the theoretical and algorithmic developments. Posterior properness was established under a Gaussian prior, leading to rigorously well-posed Bayesian inference problem. Algorithmically, the same structure yields a conditionally conjugate variational approximation with closed-form coordinate updates, providing a scalable deterministic approximation to the exact posterior and leading to a recursive estimator with exponential forgetting in the classical discounted-recursive-identification sense, suitable for streaming or slowly time-varying data.

The proposed method was illustrated on a sequential identification example from plastic recycling. As the recursive estimator is derived from the posterior structure, this example was chosen in a low-dimensional setting that permits direct comparison of the recursive variational approximation with a numerically computed reference posterior; good agreement was observed despite mild model mismatch from overlapping data. Future work will focus on an optimized $O(n^2)$ per-sample implementation exploiting the rank-one structure of the posterior precision updates, together with broader empirical study in higher-dimensional settings, including systematic sensitivity and robustness analyses.

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